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**MASTER'S PHOTO ART PROJECT
'DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINIAN FILM DISTRIBUTION IN LVIV REGION
AS A COMPONENT OF FILM PRODUCTION IN UKRAINE'****Oleksandr Bezruchko^{1a}, Nataliia Kachmar^{2b}**

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**МАГІСТЕРСЬКИЙ ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«РОЗВИТОК УКРАЇНСЬКОГО КІНОПРОКАТУ НА ЛЬВІВЩИНІ
ЯК СКЛАДОВА КІНОВИРОБНИЦТВА В УКРАЇНІ»****Олександр Безручко^{1a}, Наталія Качмар^{2b}**

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The author's idea. The idea of this Master's Photo Art Project was to draw attention to the development and decay of cinemas in the Lviv region. Cinema, since its inception, has had a great impact on people, his development, formation, more than once has returned the course of history. Cinemas are a place where you can meet its miracle face to face, touch it. However, what is the current state of Ukrainian cinemas? Who still goes there? Can we say, that at the beginning of the internet era, the cinemas are a relic of the past, which now play only a symbolic role? Having watched the cinemas of the Lviv region, communicating with employees and visitors, I tried to answer these questions, first of all for myself. Research on the development of Ukrainian film distribution is very important in modern conditions, as it is an integral component, the basic basis of cinema, which in turn is a priority of public policy in the humanitarian sphere and determined by the Laws of Ukraine 'On Culture', 'On Cinematography', etc. Successful, profitable film distribution is a financial platform for the development of film production. Therefore, in-depth analysis of ways and directions of film distribution, research of formation conditions and successful realization of its potential, study and coverage of effective principles of film network existence, construction of forecast models of its further functioning are actual and necessary for the social and economic and political development of society.

Photo No. 1

"Cinema Lives Here"
from a series of Master's Photo Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F7.1 | ISO 800 | 1/25 s

**Image No. 1 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Temperature: +18
- Exposure: +0.36
- Contrast: +7
- Highlights: +5
- Shadows: +20

Light scheme
Frame light source:
sunlight from the window.

Author's idea of photo №1. The sign 'The cinema lives here' encourages the audience of the cinema 'Lviv Film Center' to watch the film, which is on. However, although the building is located in the densely populated Frankivsk district of Lviv, even in the middle of a beautiful picturesque park called "Nut Grove", which is always a holiday for many residents, there are not enough spectators. The sign about the movie is placed here as if ironically. After all, it seems that cinema lives here, but there is nobody to watch it. It is known that cinema cannot exist without spectators.

Photo No. 2

"Planeta Kino" (*The Planet of Cinema*)
from a series of Master's Photo Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.0 | ISO 200 | 1/6 s

**Image No. 2 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Temperature: -13
- Exposure: -0.09
- Contrast: +25
- Highlights: -35
- Shadows: +18
- Texture: +35

Light scheme
Frame light source:
lamp lights.

Author's idea of photo №2. 'Planeta Kino' network is a monopolist in our country's market. It is an example of the fact that going to the cinema can be interesting, exciting and not hit the family budget. The cinema, which is located in the King Cross Leopolis shopping centre in Lviv, has an IMAX technology room with a screen size of a 5-storey building.

Of course, it is almost impossible for smaller cinemas to compete with such large corporations. Though in large cities, there is still a tendency to visit smaller and, according to Lviv residents, 'more authentic cinemas.'

Photo No. 3

'IMAX Projection System'
from a series of Master's Photo Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.0 | ISO 800 | 1/8 s

**Image No. 3 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Temperature: -46
- Exposure: +0.18
- Contrast: +18
- Highlights: -22
- Shadows: +18
- Texture: +11

Light scheme
Frame light source:
room lights.

Author's idea of photo №3. This projector in the King Cross Leopold shopping centre in the “Planeta Kino”, almost human-sized, forms a separate image for the right and left eyes, which allows the creation of a high-quality and surreal 3D effect. Of all the cinemas in the Lviv region, this projector is the largest, and there is a separate person to service it, who is always on the spot.

Photo No. 4

"New Hall" from a series
of Master's Photo Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.0 | ISO 100 | 1/13 s

**Image No. 4 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Temperature: +7
- Shade: +7
- Exposure: +1,73
- Contrast: +15
- Highlights: +11
- Shadows: +5
- Texture: +11

Light scheme
Frame light source:
room lights.

Author's idea of photo №4. In Drohobych and nearby cities, the network of 'Zlata' cinemas is a monopolist in the market. It is well deserved because cinemas located in the central parts of cities are new and clean with friendly staff. In addition, according to employees, from time to time they have meetings with actors and directors, where spectators have the opportunity to communicate with filmmakers and learn more about Ukrainian cinema.

Photo No. 5

'Meeting place' from a series
of Master's Photo Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F5.0 | ISO 800 | 1/10 s

**Image No. 5 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Temperature: -9
- Shade: -35
- Exposure: +0,09
- Contrast: +13
- Highlights: -18
- Shadows: -18
- Texture: +27

Light scheme
Frame light source:
room lights.

Author's idea of photo №5. Cinema is not just a hall or a screen. Cinema is a meeting place for friends and relatives. This is a cup of coffee before the movie. This is the expectation of the film beginning and its discussion later. This is an expectation, disappointment or admiration. Cinema is a forum, a centre and a meeting place. One such place is the Drohobych cinema 'Zlata'.

Photo No. 6

**'Observers' from a series
of Master's Photo Art Project**

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.1 | ISO 800 | 1/10 s

**Image No. 6 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Colour: black and white
- Exposure: +0,09

Light scheme
Frame light source:
room lights, lamp lights.

Author's idea photo №6. For non-cinematographers, cinema has always been something extremely magical, attractive and interesting. Everyone always wants to know how the scene is shot, how the actors play so convincingly, why some films win Oscars and others are forgotten as soon as the premiere ends. People sit quietly in the chairs of the cinema and continue to admire the film even after its completion.

Photo No. 7

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**'Kameniar Cinema' from a series
of Master's Photo Art Project**

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.0 | ISO 100 | 1/40 s

**Image No. 7 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Colour: black and white
- Temperature: -35
- Exposure: -0,18
- Contrast: +13

Light scheme
Frame light source:
sunlights.

Author's idea of photo №7. In 'Boryslav', a few steps from the central square, there is a cinema that was closed many years ago. The beautiful and symbolic name of the cinema, unfortunately, did not save it from decline and oblivion. There are no entertainment centres or recreation areas in the city, only shops and isolated cafes. According to a local woman, people move from here to more developed cities, such as Drohobych or further. Therefore, for those who remain, culture is out of time. Moreover, the cinema, as well known, cannot exist without people. The more developed the city is, the more satisfied people are - the more diverse cinemas there are. Unfortunately, 'Boryslav' did not get on this list...

Photo No. 8

'Dzvin Cinema' from a series
of Master's Photographic Art Project

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 250D /
Canon EFS 18-55 mm

Settings:
18 mm | F4.0 | ISO 800 | 1/30 s

**Image No. 8 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic:**

- Colour: black and white
- Temperature: +15
- Shade: +22
- Exposure: -0,36
- Contrast: +9
- Shadows: +5
- Sharpness: +13

Light scheme
Frame light source:
sunlights.

Author's idea of photography №8. Of all the cinemas in the Lviv region, 'Dzvin' in Lviv is in a state of decline and ruin. It is unlikely that the local authorities will ever be able to restore this building. Moreover, the people of Lviv themselves have other places to watch movies. Citizens are already accustomed to this ruined building and routinely pass by every day... Few people remember the premieres, meetings, sold-outs, old movies...

